

Impact of Glass Ceiling on Women Career Development: Moderating role of Age and Legal Factors

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Abstract- *Glass ceiling and gender discrimination are considered as biggest barriers in the professional growth of women; holding them back from occupying executive positions in the corporate world. The present research aims to analyze the prevailing effect of glass ceiling factors on women career development by examining the moderating role of age and legal factors from Pakistani women's perspective within the country. The statistical cosmos of the study consisted of 300 executive level females from different educational and health institutions through simple random sampling techniques. The study was completed with an empirical survey which was thoroughly conducted through questionnaires distributed in public and private organizations in Pakistan. The findings indicated to a significant degree the acceptance of five out of six hypotheses while one hypothesis was not proven to be true. The findings reveal that individual, organizational and family factors have a significant impact on the career development of women whereas cultural factors are not seen to have any significant impact on it. Moreover, age and legal factors moderate the relationship of cultural and organizational factors on women career development. The research is limited to specific industries and country together with a limited number of moderators providing the room for future researchers.*

Index Terms: *Glass Ceiling, Women Career Development, Age, Individual Factors, Organizational Factors, Family Role*

I. INTRODUCTION

Although women have made some gains in entering and rising executive positions in organizations worldwide, men continue to dominate senior management positions (Eagly & Carly, 2003; Eagly & Carly, 2007). This gender inequality between men and women is commonly referred to as a glass ceiling. This concept of glass ceiling has by now achieved the status of a well enriched phenomenon, supported by theory, experiment and conclusive evidence which asserts that women's career is most often blocked than men's careers (Gregg & Machin, 1993; Cassel & Walsh, 1994). As a result, women are concentrated in lower rank jobs where there are fewer opportunities for advancement in their career.

In this modern era of globalization, diversity management is essential for every organization. It requires a full stop on discrimination and thus enables employees to compete with their potential. No doubt, women are moving steadily to top positions, but many of them are still facing the discriminatory barriers blocking them to reach higher positions (Wirth, 2001).

According to a Pakistan labor force survey (2012-2013) though women represent about half of the population in Pakistan their labor force participation rate is less than men. Those who employed are usually involved in lower rank jobs like agriculture work and factory works etc. However, this noted employment rate is not applicable to senior ranks. No nation can prosper ignoring half part of its population and leaving it in discrimination.

A. Importance of the Study

This study will contribute to the filling need noted by many scholars in the empirical research to study the effect of a glass ceiling on the career development of women. This study will determine the most debated diversity issues in terms of female participation at higher management levels. This aspect is of prime importance for policyholders and decision makers. Moreover, age and legal factors have not been studied as moderating factors so far. Therefore, this study will help to highlight the actual problem and will suggest possible solutions to create maximum opportunities for executive level working females in Pakistan.

Gender equality at all levels in organizations will increase the female participation at higher management level and in decision making. Furthermore, it would be a better guideline for policymakers to develop strategies in order to overcome the issue of the glass ceiling. This study provides empirical support for gender specific model and investigates the differential impact of specific variables related to women life on the career success of women. It will be helpful for women in climbing up their career success. The findings of this research will also be helpful for identifying the things which hinder the career success of women in reaching the top level and will elaborate the ways to shatter them. It will also be helpful for male job holders in identifying the problems faced by their counterparts.

B. Study Objectives

The objective of this study is to contribute to our understanding of how glass ceiling effect on the career development of women and what role age and legal factors play in this effect. The main objectives are:

- To analyze the perception of a glass ceiling with respect to women working at an executive level in the organization.
- To measure the relationship between glass ceiling and career development of women.
- To find out the moderating role of age and legal factors on career development of women.
- To recommend the solutions for overcoming the glass ceiling effect on women career development.

C. Problem Statement and Questions of the Study

The real problem is that the representation of women in top managerial and executive positions in Pakistan is minimum due to gender discrimination which impede the women to get higher management positions in organizations. According to World Bank estimates (2014) 2.2 billion people around the globe live in poverty, (70%) of them are women, and Pakistan is no exception to this. This issue needs to be addressed seriously as gender equality in all aspects is the economic necessity of every country. Therefore, it is imperative to study the effect of glass ceiling factors on career development of women.

There is a need to identify the basic reasons behind the less female labor force participation at executive and managerial positions. The limited research done in this context needs more profound results to identify women workplace issues to address and improve policies for preventing such practices. That is why there is a need to expand the canvas on the literature of glass ceiling regarding the career development of women because in Pakistan this concept is at its emergent stage.

Based on the statement of the problem the following research questions are developed:

What is the perception of women about glass ceiling working at senior executive levels in the organizations?

What is the relationship between glass ceiling and women career development?

What role age and legal factors play in the career development of women?

What strategies should be recommended to the organizations to overcome the effect of the glass ceiling on women career development?

D. Theoretical Framework

Fig. 1 Theoretical framework

E. Study Hypothesis

The main idea emphasized by the theoretical framework above is that glass ceiling factors affect women career development. Based on the theoretical framework of the study, the following hypothesis was developed:

H₁: There is a significant impact of cultural factors on the career development of women.

H₀₁: There is no significant impact of cultural factors on the career development of women.

H₂: There is a significant impact of family factors on the career development of women.

H₀₂: There is no significant impact of family factors on the career development of women.

H₃: There is a significant impact of individual factors on career development of women.

H₀₃: There is no significant impact of individual factors on career development of women.

H₄: There is a significant impact of organizational factors on the career development of women.

H₀₄: There is no significant impact of organizational factors on the career development of women.

H₅: Age moderates the effect of cultural factors on the career development of women.

H₀₅: Age does not moderate the effect of cultural factors on the career development of women.

H₆: Legal factors moderate the effect of organizational factors on the career development of women.

H₀₆: Legal factors do not moderate the effect of organizational factors on the career development of women.

II. Literature Review

The glass ceiling is not a new concept in the literature. It is an emerging topic and has been widely studied and researched across the world (Catalyst, 1990). However, it has been researched differently by different researchers, according to the concept of the field study. It has been augmented by a

number of researchers that glass ceiling restricts the women advancement to top level positions in the organizations (Oakley, 2000; Weyer, 2007). Regardless of work done by various researchers on the glass ceiling, there is still need to investigate the causes and consequences of glass ceiling in corporate sector organizations.

A. Glass Ceiling Concept

Review of the extent literature on glass ceiling reveals a varied range of definitions and perspectives of the glass ceiling. While reviewing one may find following two groups related to the glass ceiling concept:

1). **Invisible Barriers:** The common definition of glass ceiling agreed by different researchers is, “invisible, artificial barriers that prevent qualified individuals, including women and minorities into climbing up the corporate ladder within the organization and reaching full potential” (Inman, 1998; Wirth, 2001; Glass Ceiling Commission, 2003; Lockwood, 2004; Maume, 2004; Mathur- Helm, 2006; Zeng, 2011). However, this group only mention glass ceiling with respect to one dimension, i.e., invisible hindrances. While looking at the other side of the picture, there are certain visible barriers too, like the attitude of people as mentioned by Smith and Crime (2007) which also seem to be the cause of the glass ceiling.

2). **Visible Barriers:** In contrast, the second group of researchers proposed that “there are visible barriers like attitudinal, behavioral, structural and cultural causes (stereotyping & preferred leadership style) that acts as hindrances for women and minorities in reaching top positions” (Oakley, 2000; Smith & Crimes, 2007). However, this group mentions only visible factors that are another extreme of this concept.

Derived from the arguments of both groups glass ceiling can be defined as, all the visible (organizational policies & attitudinal behavior) and invisible (gender stereotypes, family influence & unfavorable work environment) barriers prevailing in an organization that prevent all qualified persons, including women and minorities to exercise their potential on an equitable basis and hold them in reaching top level positions.

B. Glass Ceiling Models

The glass ceiling always remains a prominent issue, with many surveys and reports being undertaken internationally (Catalyst, 2007). The most important area of concern is gender differences in promotion and under-representation of women at the executive level, suggesting the sign of glass ceiling in the organizations (Eagly & Carli, 2007; Adams et al., 2009). One might find the following four models related to literature of glass ceiling:

1). **Equal Opportunity Model:** This model is based on the concept that in seeking leadership opportunities men and women face the same issues and problems, and women choose to join lower risk jobs upon their own discretion (Lockwood, 2004). It means there is no existence of a glass ceiling at the top level and women choose to remain at a low level. This concept is also supported by Schambaugh (2008) who said that women had placed obstacles in their career advancement by themselves.

2). **Personal Insight Model:** This model is referred to a belief that women are able to break the glass ceiling, for example, “the more women seek senior positions, the easier it will be for the followers” (Catalyst, 1998; Eagly & Carli, 2007; Adams et al., 2009). This shows that by developing good insight and capability, women can contribute to breaking the glass ceiling by representing gender equality goals. Moreover, women can also break the glass ceiling by exhibiting masculine behavior because femininity is considered to be non-authoritative.

3). **Resignation Model:** This model is referred to the concept that women when pursuing career advancement suffer much more negative consequences than men, for example, women are more likely to be hurt than men when they seek promotions to top level, face jealousy from co-workers and most importantly women careers are considered to be negatively affected by maternal wall (Fassinger, 2008; O’ Neil et al., 2008). These key barriers identified are the lack of transparency around promotion policies, work-family conflict, unfavorable work environment, the difference in pay gap and lower placement of women.

4). **Personal Preference Model:** This model promotes the belief that women prefer their life goals, such as family involvement rather than promotions and career development, they do not want high powered positions, left prestigious jobs to raise children and give up their independent income (Mathur-Helm, 2006; Boushey, 2008; Smith, Crittenden & Caputi, 2012). Moreover, another important reason for women to left job is described by Stone (2007), who stated that “women take this decision because of gender inequality at home as their spouse wants them to be involved in family responsibilities.”

Regardless of the culture and origin of the country the presence of glass ceiling is cross culturally observed by researchers in different countries such as U.S (Powell & Butterfield, 1994), Bangladesh (Afza & Newaz, 2008), Singapore (Man, M. Mok, K., Dimovski, M., & Skerlavaj, V., 2010), India (Sharma, Sharma & Kaushik, 2011), Australia (Smith, Crittenden & Caputi, 2012), Pakistan (Jabbar & Imran, 2013) and Korea (Rowley, 2013). These researchers identified different glass ceiling factors in these countries that act as obstacles in front of women seeking promotions to top-level positions. However, the intensity is different from country to country. This might be because of a different culture, traditions and different stereotypes prevailing in these countries.

C. Women Career Development

Career development can be defined as social, psychological, physical and economic activities in which individuals participate to improve themselves relative to their work roles (London & Stumpf, 1982). This definition is limited to certain activities of an individual life, but it didn’t mention the levels of involvement through which individual goes by developing skills and abilities. Another group of researchers typically defined career development as an ongoing series of stages characterized by unique concerns, themes and tasks, and these tasks happen at more or less predictable times during the course of a career (Greenhaus et al., 2000; O’Neil & Bilimoria, 2005). However, apart from these unique tasks, certain other factors are also taken into consideration by various researchers, like willingness to take risks, abilities to do tough tasks and

power to take right decisions that constitute career development.

It is argued that the nature of women career development is different from men in many aspects like experience and family responsibilities (Phillips & Imkof, 1997). Supplement to this Gallos (1989) and Cafferella, Clark, and Ingram (1997) also argued that career development of women is different as compared to men as a result of the developmental difference between men and women as women are participative, collaborative and confident and embrace different styles of their workforce. The literature also suggests that women experience more interruptions in progressing through a career as compared to men (Bierema, 1998).

In the light of women opportunity to reach top positions, it seemed appropriate to investigate the factors that act as obstacles to women's careers as they strive for executive positions in the organizations. One might divide these factors as individual factors, cultural factors, family factors, organizational factors, and environmental factors.

1). Individual Factors: This group is of the view that different psychological profiles of the sexes share difference between masculinity and femininity. It means that men and women leaders behave somewhat differently because gender role exerts some influence on a leadership role (Eagly, 1987; Wood & Eagly, 2002; Weyer, 2006). In contrast to this another group of researchers not only discuss the assumptions about men having superior capabilities for leadership (Eagly & Johannesen-Schmidt, 2001) but also stated that women managers relatively earn lower income as compared to their male counterparts and less likely to reach top positions (Lyness & Thompson, 2000; Vanhala, 2009). Literature also suggests that an individual's skills and abilities to do work are culturally recognized and strongly affect their career advancement.

2). Cultural Factors: Cultural factors argue that socio cultural structures, systems and arrangements, lack of informal advice, glass walls, status belief, sexual harassment, stereotypes, uncomfortable feeling and doubt of men and high standards of performance for women as compared to men for same job are the cause for differences in leadership attributed to females (Beger et al., 1980; Fisher, 1992; Martin, 1992). International labor organization (ILO) (2004) also stated cultural biases and women's status not as a bread earner. These are the major constraints to the career advancement of women. Moreover, it is also seen that men in managerial positions always prefer people with similar cultural preferences as their own (Kanter, 1997). This would definitely lead to a stop on the career advancement of women in their profession.

3). Family Factors: This group states that family is an important factor affecting the career development of women. Recent researches have investigated the impact of contextual factors, most importantly family relationships on women's career success (O' Neil & Bilimoria, 2005). Women's world is thought to be associated with particular roles like care for others and the maintenance of relationships, encounter conflict between work and family (Mavin, 2001; Mainiero & Sullivan, 2005). However, there are some examples of work life balance in women 's lives and some females succeed in the organizations while maintaining their family responsibilities.

4). Organizational Factors: This group states that organizational practices seem to play an important role in the career development of women. In an organization, there are lots of processes, structural factors, policies and set criteria that have unclear rules and regulations which are key issues for women's position and possibilities in the organizations (Morrison, White & Velsor, 1987; Flanders, 1994; Vanhala, 2009). These studies concluded that internal organizational culture is mostly male dominated and seem to be less supportive of female leadership. This might be because of the reason that in some societies organizations prefer male culture because they see women as less ambitious as compared to men. This can also be justified by the study of Sachein (1975) who states that there are some qualities that reside more in men than women like leadership, confidence, competitiveness, aggression, ambition, and responsibility.

5). Environmental Factors: Relationship between women career development and environmental factors has been a focus of the research stream. There is a number of researchers tracking the effect of environmental factors on the career development of women. Different researchers have given different meanings to environmental factors. One group of researchers has suggested that infrastructure, legal, economic regulation, and social, cultural variables are environmental factors that affect women career advancement (Ronstadt, 1984; ILO, 1998). On the other hand, another group of researchers has included developmental settings (Keeble & Waliker, 1994) supportive services (Minniti & Arenius, 2003) and infrastructure, technical skill, abilities, new markets and governmental influences (Mansor, 2005) in environmental factors. Nevertheless, different indicators of environmental factors are used by different researchers, but all of them have included legal and governmental influence as a major indicator of the environmental factor.

All of above five groups mentioned the effect of the glass ceiling on women career development. These groups have studied the effect of one or two glass ceiling factors on women career advancement. This study has investigated the collective effect of all these glass ceiling factors on the career development of women.

III. Research Methodology

A. Study Population

The unit of analysis of the current study comprised of executive level female employees from two corporate sectors, i.e., health and education sectors of Pakistan. The heterogeneous population is selected to have diverse representation from different working setups. A random selection of nine organizations (5 from public and 4 from private sectors) was made from three major cities, i.e., Lahore, Multan, and Bahawalpur. The information was obtained through two sources, i.e., questionnaire and interviews. The researcher distributed (342) questionnaires to all females working at executive levels. (300) questionnaires were returned with (87.7%) rate of return.

B. Research Instrument

The research instrument used for the study was questionnaire and interviews. The questionnaire administered by A Chamaru De Alwis, University of Kelaniya was used. Written approval for the use of the questionnaire was taken from the professor. However, part

A and part C of the questionnaire was designed by the researcher. The parts of the questionnaire are:

1). **Part one- personal information:** In this part, respondents were asked to indicate their gender, age, marital status, level of education, job title, and experience.

2. **Part Two- Research Dimensions:** this part consists of three dimensions; the first dimension is independent variables- glass ceiling factors which contain (27) items. Individual factors include items from (11 to 19), items related to cultural factors are from (20 to 25), items from (26 to 31) related to family factors and items from (32-37) are related to organizational factors. The questionnaire was represented with strongly disagree forming the one end of the continuum to agree at the other end strongly. These were presented in numbers from (1 to 5). The second dimension- dependent variable- is women career development consist of sixteen items from (38 to 53). Items from (38 to 43) were related to a career focused, attitude towards organization represent items from (44 to 48) and items from (49 to 53) were related to family support.

The third dimension- moderating variables- were legal factors consists of 8 items. Items from (54 to 57) were related to EEO laws and items from (58 to 61) were related to OFCCP.

C. Study Validity and Reliability

Although the questionnaire was adopted and the author has already checked the validity of the adopted questionnaire, therefore, it was not necessary to check its validity. However, to further justify the validity and to generalize the results of the study the validity of the questionnaire was checked through factor analysis. Prior to factor analysis, KMO and Bartlett’s test of Sphericity was performed to measure sampling adequacy and to test data fit for factor analysis. The present research has KMO value near to 1 and significance level of Bartlett’s test of Sphericity as $p < 0.05$ as suggested by Field (2005).

Factor components were presented as factor loading to interpret the result of factor analysis. Items with loading less than 0.4 were dropped from the instrument. Varimax rotation was used to rotate the extracted factors. The internal consistency and reliability of the present study were measured through Cronbach Alpha. The Cronbach Alpha for the present study was 0.7.

D. Statistical Methods for the Study

In order to check the comparison between two demographic groups and to test the hypothesis following tests were used: T test, ANOVA, Kolmogorov-Smirnov and Shapiro-Wil tests, correlation analysis and regression analysis.

E. Data Presentation and Analysis

1). **A Profile of the Sample:** The respondent profile summary is shown in the table below:

Table (1) Frequencies and percentages of demographic factors of the sample

Demographics	Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage%
Gender	Male	0	0
	Female	300	100

Age	25-30	22	7.3
	31-35	74	24.7
	36-40	103	34.3
	41- onward	101	33.7
Marital status	Single	75	25
	Married	225	74
Education	Graduate	14	4.7
	Postgraduate	193	64.3
	Doctorate	83	27.7
	Post doctorate	10	3.3
Current designation	Supervisory level	17	5.7
	Middle management level	225	75
	Senior management level	58	19.3
Number of promotions	1	135	45
	2	101	33.7
	3	53	17.7
	4	11	3.7
Working years	1-5	87	29
	6-10	171	57
	11-15	35	11.7
	16 or more	7	2.3
Total experience	1-5	76	25.3
	6-10	182	60.7
	11-15	33	11
	16 or more	9	3

F. Descriptive Statistics

Mean of overall responses was calculated to check the variability of responses. The table below depicts the results of the mean calculated from the responses:

Table (2) summary of data description

Scale	Subscale	No. of items	Mean (n=300)
Glass ceiling factors		27	2.61
	Individual factors	9	2.38
	Cultural factors	6	2.01
	Family factors	6	2.63
	Organizational factors	6	3.55
Women career development		16	3.72
	Career focused	6	3.71
	Attitude towards organization	5	3.8
	Family support	5	3.6
Legal factors		8	2.29
	EEO laws	4	2.3
	OFCCP	4	2.29

The table above shows that the mean value of subscale women’s career development is high as compared to the other two scales. However, all the variables have a small mean score which shows less

dispersion of the responses among the sample and hence they are uniform.

G. Hypothesis Testing

1). Independent variables: Simple regression analysis has been done (for first 4 hypothesis) to predict the change in outcome variable from the predictor variable. Following the general equation is used in predicting the data.

$$Y_i = (b_0 + b_1X_i) + \epsilon_i$$

2). Combine Effect of Glass Ceiling Factors on WDC: In order to justify the first four hypotheses, all four factors of glass ceiling were regressed together. The results are shown in the table:

Table (3) regression analysis of all glass ceiling factors (N=300)

Variables	B	SE	T	F	R	R ²	P
Constant	.195	.172	1.133	158.039	.826	.628	.001
Cultural factors	-.009	.056	-.170				.865
Individual factors	.418	.072	5.804				.000
Family factors	.226	.065	3.455				.001
Organizational factors	.535	.039	13.741				.000

It is evident from the table (3) above that all glass ceiling factors affect the career development of women except cultural factors. The significance value of cultural factors is .865 which is greater than .01. The value of R² shows that glass ceiling factors contribute (62%) variation in women career development. Thus combine effect of glass ceiling factors on women career development is found significant.

3). Moderating Variables: Multiple regression analysis was used to test hypothesis 5 and 6. The equation used in testing of hypothesis 5 is given below:
 $Y = b_0 + b_1cX + B_2M + B_3cX * M$

Table (4) multiple regression analysis for hypothesis 5 (N=300)

Variables	B	SE	T	F	R	R ²
Model 1						
Constant	3.256	.181	17.979	5.653	.136	.019
Cultural factors	0.206	.087	2.378			
Model 2						
Constant	2.997	.088	34.154	24.650	.501	.251
Cultural factors	.319	.077	4.134			
Young vs middle age	1.222	.183	6.688			
Young vs. quarter age	1.021	.116	8.813			
Young vs aged	.690	.114	6.031			

The table (4) shows the moderated regression analysis between cultural factors, age, and women career development. As age is a categorical variable, therefore it is necessary for regression

analysis to change it into dummy variables first. That is why age is converted into three dummy variables as shown in the table above. Model 1 explains the effect of cultural factors on women career development. Model 2 describes the moderating effect of age on model 1.

The value of R in model 1 and 2 is .136 and .501 respectively. It means that moderator strengthens the relationship of cultural factors on women career development. The value of R² in the first model shows only (1.9%) variation while in model 2 it shows that age (moderator) explain (25%) variation in women career development. These results show that age significantly moderates the effect of cultural factors on women career development.

The equation used for testing hypothesis 6 is given below:

$$Y = b_0 + b_1cX + B_2cM + B_3cX * cM$$

Table (5) multiple regression analysis for hypothesis 6 (N=300)

Variables	B	SE	T	F	R	R ²
Model 1						
Constant	3.637	.027	132.888	344.759	.836	.699
Cultural factors	0.638	0.209	21.870			
Legal factors	.3406	.036	9.341			
Model 2						
Constant	3.694	.025	146.077	314.094	.872	.761
organizational factors	.5339	.029	18.545			
Legal factors	.3763	.033	11.476			
Organizational legal factors	-.3156	.036	-8.761			

Hypothesis 6 is tested using moderated multiple regression. Results are presented in two models. Model 1 represented the results of regression before moderation applied. Model 2 represents the results when the moderator is applied. The value of R for both models depicts that legal factors moderate the effect of organizational factors on women career development. The value of R² for model 1 and 2 is .699 and .761 respectively. This shows that before moderation organizational factors describe (69%) of variation and after moderation organizational factors account for (76%) of variation in women career development. Thus legal factors significantly moderate the effect of organizational factors on the career development of women.

IV. Research Findings

The first hypothesis of the study was to investigate the impact of cultural factors on the career development of women. The results revealed no significant relationship between these two variables. This finding does not confirm prior expectations and complementing previous researchers (Berger et al., 1980; Fisher. 1992; Bartol et al.,

2003). This may be due to the fact that every country has its own values, standards, and stereotypes that are embedded in the roots of the society. No doubt, women are a critical part of every society, but cultural beliefs and traditions of every country have its own impact on career advancement whether they are performing caregiving duties or fulfilling their professional responsibilities. However, these results are to some extent consistent with the study of Bombuwela and Chamaru (2013) that reveal that there is a moderate negative relationship between cultural factors and women career advancement.

The second hypothesis postulates that family factors have a significant impact on women career development. The findings show a significant positive correlation between family factors and women career development. This research is consistent with previous research findings (Friedman & Greenhaus, 2000; Hewelett, 2002; Kirchmeyer, 2002; O'Neil & Bilimoria, 2005) that confirmed the associations between women's career success and their family roles. This is due to the fact that family accounts for the larger context in women's lives. However, one study by Chamaru (2013) in Sri Lanka has found an inconsistency with a current study by stating that family factors have no significant influence on the career development of women. This may be due to reasonable differences in social values and traditions of Sri Lanka and Pakistan.

The third hypothesis proposed that there is a significant impact of individual factors on women career development. The results show a positive correlation between individual factors and women career development. Consistent with previous research findings (Aycan, 2004; Dorfman, Hanges & Brodbeck, 2004; House et al., 2004) individual factors are proven to have a significant impact on the career development of women. However, different researchers have considered different traits to be included in individual factors. Acceptance of hypothesis three has revealed that individual factors have a significant impact on the career development of women. This might be because of individual skills, abilities, and confidence that contribute a lot to the success of an individual.

It was hypothesized in the fourth hypothesis that organizational factors have a significant impact on the career development of women. The findings show a significant positive relationship between both variables. The finding is consistent with previous researches (Morrison, White & Velsor, 1987; Flanders, 1994; Rowley, 2013). This confirms that organizational practices and policies are evidenced worldwide, often compounded by traditional gender role to affect the career progress of women.

The fifth hypothesis of the study proposed that age moderates the effect of cultural factors on the career development of women. Findings show that age significantly affects the career development of women. This proposition was based on the study conducted by Bombuwela & Chamaru (2013). Numerous factors have been studied as moderators between glass ceiling factors and women career development. Though age has not been studied previously as moderating factor between cultural factors and women career development. However, the

effect of age on women career development has been studied by various researchers (Jabbar & Imran, 2013).

Six hypothesis stated that legal factors moderate the effect of organizational factors on women career development. Although a number of researches had focused on glass ceiling and women career development and studied the role of legal factors non career development of women but very little attention is given to the moderating role of legal factors. However, researchers (Bombuwela & Chjamaru, 2013) have proposed that moderating effect of legal factors on career development of women can be studied. This study indicates the significant moderating effect of legal factors on women career development.

V. Conclusion

Thus it is concluded that glass ceiling factors that are evidenced in the literature to have significant impact on career development of women are also prevailing in developing countries like Pakistan. It was hypothesized that age and legal factors moderate the effect of cultural and organizational factors on career development of women which is found to be true. The results from analyzed data are significant at less than (5%) significance level or confidence interval of more than (95%). Female leaders can enhance the competitiveness of business, the question should not concentrate on the difference between male and female leaders but on what both of them can contribute to the organizations. The present study is meaningful as it proposes an integrated model which shows glass ceiling factors along with their relationship with women career development and provides practical implications.

VI. Recommendations

There are some suggestions based on the current research that may act as a meaningful guide for further studies:

- The research can also include other variables that affect the career development of women like environmental factors, type and size of industry and task.
- The study is conducted on women in top management positions, but future researches should investigate women at all levels i.e., entry, middle and top management level in order to know how much hindrances they face to get next grade.
- There is a room for more knowledge to be gained by studying and comparing the effects of different cultures and countries on how the organizations' and government's structure affect women's status as leaders.
- Policy makers and management should develop better guidelines and strategies for working women in order to overcome issues of glass ceiling.
- Female job holders should identify the things that hinder their career success and should shatter the glass ceiling.
- Organizations and management should understand the women's caring responsibilities and should help them in developing a family friendly organizational culture and atmosphere.

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